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The study explores the challenges in selecting suitable materials for engineering applications, focusing on metallurgical studies and microscopic analysis of heat-treated steel from crankshafts.

Key points
crankshafts
quenching
heat treatment
hardness test
Microscopic image
image analysis

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Abstract

In the process of selecting a material, both physical and mechanical properties matter from which it can be determined where those materials can be used. The quality of a material is decided by analysis of its properties. Hence, microstructure analysis, and metallurgical studies have been developing its segment in a broader sense each day. This field of research is to identify the characteristics of a material or any metal that includes ductility, softness, toughness, stiffness, yield strength, tensile strength, corrosion resistance, and many other properties. These properties can be changed by heat treatment, hardening and tempering. Multiple processes can be implemented on a material or metal to induce a certain quality for the appropriate usage. However, there are some challenges in choosing the right metal as the requirements are often not

fulfilled or half fulfilled. *This work is focused on a carbon steel taken from a car crankshaft to analyze the changes in properties after being subjected to different kinds of heat treatments, and how hardness, tensile strength, ductility change with the microstructural behavior and formation of martensitic structure. Then the result was verified by the theoretical findings. Some observations have been included for the possible reasons that caused a few challenges in studying the microstructure of the parent steel. A significant part of this experiment was to work with mild carbon steel- BSRM and KSRM rods. The findings of the mechanical characteristics of KSRM and BSRM steel have been used to establish a comparison and to give a decision from the perspective of current Bangladesh. Therefore, a survey was conducted with a small community of experts in selecting materials and outstandingly the experimental decision matched their decision and BSRM has been considered to be the best-suited mild carbon steel rod.*

Introduction:

Metallography in its broadest definition encompasses all aspects of the characterization of the structure of metals and alloys, and the objects made from them, in relation to their composition and properties (Askeland 2014, 10), Another is Microstructure, which can be defined as the structure of a prepared surface or thin foil of material as revealed by a microscope above 25× magnification. Initially cast iron, alloy, mild carbon steel, and high carbon steel. are selected to carry out metallography and microscopic structure investigations. An automobile crankshaft's high carbon steel has been gathered and chosen for heat treatment examination. Heat treatment is frequently used to modify a metallic alloy's mechanical characteristics. Heat treatment is changing a metal's mechanical properties, such as its strength, brittleness, machinability, and hardness (“Heat Treatment Processes for Steel – IspatGuru” 2020). Ultimately, this technical paper's key features are the comparison of heat-treated characteristics, the microstructure mechanical properties of the crankshaft specimen, and the analysis of KSRM and BSRM Steel.

The characteristics of strength, ductility, toughness, hardness, and corrosion resistance can all be changed in metals with heat treatment. At high temperatures, metals and alloys exhibit a variety of phenomena. For instance, austenite's breakdown and recrystallization. When the right heat treatments or thermal procedures are applied, these can effectively change the mechanical properties. It is a widespread practice to apply heat treatments to commercial alloys. Annealing, quenching, tempering, and precipitation hardening are examples of common heat treatment procedures (“Thermal Processing of Metals | nuclear-power.com”, n.d.).

Annealing process consists of heating the steel to the proper temperature and then cooling slowly through the transformation range, preferably in the furnace or in any good heat-insulating material. The slow cooling is generally continued to low temperatures. The purpose of annealing is to refine grains, inducing ductility, toughness, softness, increase mechanical properties, etc.

Normalizing can be done by heating the steel approximately 100ferrenhite above the upper critical temperature followed by slow cooling to room temperature in still air. Purposes of normalizing is to induce toughness.

Hardening is a metallurgical metalworking process used to increase the hardness of a metal (Cobb 2021).

Quenching is a process of cooling, as by immersion in oil or water, of a metal object from the high temperature at which it has been shaped (“Quenching | Heat Treatment, Hardening & Tempering” 2023). This study will examine two different quenchant media.

Figure 1. Heat treatment strategies with different quenching and tempering process

Oil is widely used in quenching because it transmits heat rapidly and

without introducing large distortions. (Cobb 2021)

Water is one of the first quenchant and is now one of the blacksmiths' most popular quenching techniques. Water is an effective quenchant for quick cooling due to its high heat capacity. As a result, a significant amount of martensite forms on the metal's surface. However, the workpiece is more likely to experience distortions as an outcome (Cobb 2021).

Figure 2. CCT Diagram of both water and oil quenched

In this paper, a steel specimen from a crankshaft is randomly selected and then subjected to different heat treatment methods. The treated samples are tested for their hardness and photographed under a microscope for an image analysis to be done on their microstructure. In 2018 Mr. K. Aliakbari and his team worked on the micrograph of the crankshaft after getting etched and the results of hardness tests showed that the surface of the part underwent surface hardness and had a smaller microstructure than the central part. (K., n.d.). Heat-treated steel is used to improve strength and lower costs from alloy usage; however, the lowered costs may be associated with disadvantages such as low steel ductility or failure to pass flexural strength tests. Studies conducted after the 921 earthquake in 1999 (Chen et al., 2000, Chen.,2006) have reported that because heat-treated steel features relatively unstable properties, using such steel in

welding, bar splicing, or thread-cutting components in structures may result in a lack of resistance to seismic activity. Currently, there are many challenges in choosing metal for different engineering applications. This research aims to verify the existing findings and seek for any irregular error that can be a factor in changing mechanical properties. Therefore, high carbon steel is heat treated to analyze microstructure, tensile strength, hardness, and ductility. A huge part of this research is run on the mild carbon steel, KSRM, and BSRM which are to be examined to analyze the challenges of choosing the best-suited rod in structural engineering. A survey on the opinion of experts on the selection of materials has been conducted. The goal is to match their decision with our experimental decision in establishing a better perspective for the selection process protecting the interest of our shareholders through sustainable growth and value creation. In this study, the tensile strength, hardness, and microstructure of both the KSRM and BSRM specimens are examined to figure out the challenges in depth.

Methodology:

Figure 3. Working methodology flow chart analysis

Heat treatment:

Heat-treatment is an operation or combination of operations involving|

heating a metal or alloy in its solid state to a **certain temperature** at the maximum available heating rate.

holding it there for a specified time, and

cooling it to the room temperature at a predetermined rate to obtain desired grain structure and corresponding properties.

Table for temperature and cooling method of specific heat-treated specimen

Specimen	Cooling Condition	Heating Temperature (Approx)
Annealing	Inside Furnace	910°C
Normalizing	Air Cooling	
Oil Quenched	Oil Cooling	
Water Quenched	Water Cooling	

Cutting a specimen and Mounting:

To mount the high carbon steel sample into a conductive material such as bakelite or epoxy resin using a hot press or clod mounting technique, the sample was cut into a smaller size. The sample was then completely encircled by it to prevent edge rounding during grinding and polishing.

Figure 4 a diagram of an ideal mounted specimen

Rough Polishing and Fine Polishing:

After a component of the metal specimen's surface was first rough polished or paper ground in the following order: 60, 120, 240, 320, 600, 800, 1000, 1200, and 1500. This was done with the use of abrasive paper. It is used to scrape off the surface layer to bring

a solid solution surface to be etched. To create a sequence of parallel scratch lines on the sample's surface, a modest amount of force was applied as the sample was moved back and forth in a single direction throughout the grinding process. Subsequently, the scratch surface was turned 90 degrees, and each time, a finer paper was substituted for the abrasive one. Following that, the specimen was transported to be finely polished using aluminum oxide, which was applied at a speed of 300–400 RPM until a mirror-like surface was obtained. This was done by creating a paste with water. It can effectively remove scratches, oxidation, and other imperfections, leaving a smooth and reflective finish.

Figure 5. Series polish paper and polishing wheel machine

Figure 6. Microscopic view of scratches by paper grinder (A) and fine polished mirror surface (B)

Etching:

Following that, acetone swab with cotton was swatched over the surface in case any grease was left, for its highly volatile characteristic, it was evaporated along with water and grease. **2% Nital (2% nitro acid, 98% methanol)** was used to etch the mirror surface. To prevent further etching, the item was cleaned once again with acetone. boundaries and defects.

Figure 7. Etching of metals

Etching is a selective chemical attack used to reveal metal microstructure and remove deformed layers. It creates contrast in alloys with multiple phases, affecting the rate and revealing different features. Etchantants preferentially attack high energy sites.

Image capturing and software analysis:

The sample was put under the Metallurgical Microscope for microscopic view at (1000X) magnification power, Ideally the surface to be examined optically should be flat and level. If it is not, the image will pass in and out of focus as the viewing area is moved across the surface. (“Sample Preparation”, 2020)

Table for magnification power is used in specific experiment

Specimen	Eyepiece	Objective	Magnification Power
1	10x	100x	1000x
2	10x	100x	1000x
3,4,5,6,7,8	10x	20x	200x
		100x	1000x

To determine the carbon content in the sample the microstructure needed to be analyzed. Thus a Java-based open-source image processing software; **ImageJ** was used to create contrast between the different phases present in the structure.

- A black and white picture of the microstructure was opened in the software
- Using the threshold effect the area fraction of black and the white region was determined from the picture

- The area measurement and particle counting algorithm detected the area percentage of different phases and the wt% of pearlite and alpha ferrite.

ImageJ is a Java-based image processing program developed at the National Institutes of Health and the Laboratory for Optical and Computational Instrumentation (LOCI, University of Wisconsin). Its first version, ImageJ 1.x, is developed in the public domain, while ImageJ2 and the related projects SciJava, ImgLib2, and SCIFIO are licensed with a permissive BSD-2 license. (“ImageJ” 2015)

Figure 8. Picture from ImageJ software

Figure 9.

Picture of a specimen of normalized medium carbon steel

Figure 10.

Picture of Brinell hardness test machine

Hardness test:

After that samples were subjected to Brinell hardness test. The specimens were put under a machine that put force by a pointy needle. It created a very small hole in the specimen.

Then calculating the diameters and using Brinell's law BHN and Ultimate Tensile strength were obtained.

Following certain steps were taken to obtain the BHN.

- The testing sample was placed on the anvil.
- A ball indenter is used to apply a preliminary test force, often known as a preload or small load, on a sample.
- The zero or reference point that penetrates the surface to lessen the impacts of surface finish is represented by this load. The major load is applied after the preload to achieve the total amount of test load that is needed.
- To provide time for elastic recovery, this force is maintained for a predefined duration of about 20 seconds.
- The final position is then compared to the position obtained from the preload, the indentation depth variance between the preload value and the main load, and this major load is released.
- This process was applied two to three times in different places of the same specimen surface to get an average value of depth.

Storage of the specimen in a desiccator:

Finally the specimen was kept in a silicon gel-based desiccator to prevent it from moisture. Desiccators are sealable enclosures containing desiccants used for preserving moisture-sensitive items such as cobalt chloride paper for other uses. A common use for desiccators is to protect chemicals that are hygroscopic or that react with water from humidity.

Figure 11. Picture of Brinell hardness test machine

Result and Calculation:

The microscopic structure of each specimen has been collected. Specimens are as bellow:

1. Original (From crankshaft)

2. Annealed Medium Carbon Steel
3. Normalized Medium Carbon Steel
4. Oil Quenched Medium Carbon Steel
5. Water Quenched Medium Carbon Steel
6. Cast Iron
7. KSRM Mild Carbon Steel
8. BSRM Mild Carbon Steel

Among these 8 specimens, Experiments No. 2,3,4,5 are based on heat treatment, and 7 and 8 no experiment is for comparison of KSRM and BSRM

Microscopic Structure

The pictures that were taken with the microscope (A) specific grayscale zones of greatest focus (B) and the selective crystal masks the image analysis program produced (C) are displayed in Figures 12 to 19:

Figure 12 shows the microstructure original (cranksheft) sample und microscope (A), Red masks of the chosen pearlite (dark) ferrite matrix (C), and grayscale of the o focus region (B)

	Calculation	
	Area	Percentage
Total area	786432	100
Total pearlite area	618182.7379	78.606
Total ferrite area	168249.2621	21.394
Carbon content	0.63055952	wt%

Figure 13: The microstructure of an annealed sample observed through a microscope (A).

The grayscale of the optimal focus region (B) and the dark red masks of the chosen pearlite crystals in the ferrite matrix (C)

Annealed of steel

	Calculation	
	Area Percentage	
Total area	1253376	100
Total pearlite area	688943.1859	54.967
total alpha ferrite area	564432.8141	45.033
Carbon content	0.44333864	wt%

Figure 14: The microstructure of a Normalized sample observed through a microscope (A).

The grayscale of the optimal focus region (B) and the dark red masks of the chosen pearlite crystals in the ferrite matrix ©

Normalizing of steel

	Calculation	
	Area Percentage	
Total area	1253376	100
Total pearlite area	817696.2355	65.2395
total alpha ferrite area	435679.7645	34.7605
Carbon content	0.52469684	wt%

Figure 15: The microstructure of an oil Quenched Medium carbon steel sample observed through a microscope in 200X magnification (A).

The grayscale of the optimal focus region in 200X magnification (B)

The microstructure of an oil Quenched Medium carbon steel sample observed through a microscope in 1000X magnification (A).

The grayscale of the optimal focus region in 1000X magnification (B)

Figure 16: The microstructure of a Water Quenched Medium Carbon Steel sample observed through a microscope in 200X magnification (A).

The grayscale of the optimal focus region in 200X magnification (B)

The microstructure of a Water Quenched Medium Carbon Steel sample observed through a microscope in 1000X magnification (A).

The grayscale of the optimal focus region in 1000X magnification (B)

Figure 17: The microstructure of a cast iron sample observed through a microscope in 200X magnification (A).

The grayscale of the optimal focus region in 200X magnification (B)

The microstructure of a cast iron sample observed through a microscope in 1000X magnification (A).

The grayscale of the optimal focus region in 1000X magnification (B)

Figure 18: The microstructure of a KSRM rod sample observed through a microscope (A). The grayscale of the optimal focus region (B) and the dark red masks of the chosen pearlite crystals in the ferrite matrix (C)

KSRM of steel

	Calculation	
	Area	Percentage
Total area	5013504	100
Total pearlite area	3084207.391	61.518
total alpha ferrite area	1929296.609	38.482
Carbon content	0.49522256	wt%

Figure 19: The microstructure of a BSRM steel sample observed through a microscope (A).

The grayscale of the optimal focus region (B)

and the dark red masks of the chosen pearlite crystals in the ferrite matrix (C)

BSRM of steel

	Calculation	
	Area	Percentage
Total area	786432	100
Total pearlite area	310860.841	39.528
total alpha ferrite area	475571.159	60.472
Carbon content	0.32106176	wt%

Carbon Content Calculation Formula:

The formula that is used to calculate carbon content is for hypo eutectoid steel.

$$Wt\% C = (0.80)(\% \text{ of pearlite area}) + (0.008)(\% \text{ of ferrite area})$$

Figure 20. Bar chart of carbon content vs specimens

Brinell Hardness

The Brinell hardness testing method was the first hardness tester used in the industry. Usually, this testing process takes 10 to 30 seconds and is accomplished by pressing a spherical indenter of a certain diameter against the testing surface of the material sample. The formula used to measure the hardness of each specimen is

$$BHN = \frac{2F}{\pi D(D - \sqrt{D^2 - d^2})}$$

Here,

F= The force applied in kg

D= The diameter in mm of the spherical indenter used

d= The average depth in mm

Tensile Strength

The BHN can be converted into the ultimate tensile strength (UTS). The relation between Tensile strength and

BHN is as follows:

$$\text{Tensile Strength} = BHN \times 0.3515 \times 9.81$$

The unit of Tensile strength is N/mm²

Table for BHN number and Tensile strength

Specimen	Load(F)	Ball diameter (D)	Depth (d)	BHN (experimental)	BHN (standard)	Tensile Strength (experimental)	Tensile Strength (standard)	Error % (BHN)	Error% (TS)
Original high carbon steel	187.5 kg	2.5mm	0.84mm	328.5	329	1132.7	1100	0.15%	2.19%
Annealing	187.5 kg	2.5mm	1mm	228.76	229	788.8	772	0.10%	2.17%
Normalizing	187.5 kg	2.5mm	0.75mm	414.6	415	1429.6	1421	0.09%	0.60%
Water quenched	187.5 kg	2.5mm	0.5mm	945.2	945	3259.5		0.02%	
Oil quenched	187.5 kg	2.5mm	0.62mm	611.3	601.5	2108	2039	1.60%	3.30%
Cast Iron	187.5 kg	2.5mm	0.93mm	266.118	266	917.63	911	0.04%	0.72%
KSRM	187.5 kg	2.5mm	1.05mm	206.52	207	712.14	695	0.23%	2.40%
BSRM	187.5 kg	2.5mm	0.95mm	254.6	255	877.92	865	0.15%	1.50%

Discussion:

Many phenomena occur in metals and alloys at elevated temperatures. For example, recrystallization and the decomposition of austenite. It has a remarkable effect on the properties, the phases, and the solid solutions of the metal. The sample of high-carbon steel was straightly taken from a car crankshaft which was then heat treated. Then a cast iron alloy was selected as a sample as well as mild carbon steel, BSRM, and KSRM from a construction site. Each experiment was analyzed in the same process and the result can be divided into 4 segments to compare mechanical properties which are 1. Carbon content and mechanical properties 2. Heat Treatment 3. Alloy structure analysis 4. Comparison between KSRM and BSRM

Carbon content

Figure 21. Bar chart of carbon content vs specimens

High Carbon Steel (Original)

Generally, crankshaft is made from mild carbon steel as high carbon steel is very hard and least ductile. But the calculation shows that it is high carbon steel. Theoretically, the carbon content range of any plain high carbon steel is 0.60 wt% to 1.40 wt%. Experimentally it was found an average percentage of 1.34 wt% of carbon content which means it is a hypereutectoid steel. Then again the microstructure shows a visibility of a cementite network which is unlikely for high carbon steel due to much higher than the usual cases. High carbon steels with greater than 0.8% carbon have a pearlitic matrix within a cementite network. (McSwine 2023)

The reasons behind this might be:

1. We are unaware of the fact that how the material was processed or heated for crankshaft. There might be some alloys or impurities doped in mild carbon steel that caused the increment of carbon content.

2. What kind of heat treatment was subjected to the parent element is unknown, even different kinds of heating treatment could have been implemented.
3. Simply they took a high carbon steel for any special purpose
4. The specimen was manually polished and thus some places on the image were a little blurry and it is unknown how the image analysis software functions in such cases
5. Although errors are very few that are calculated regarding the standard value, some of the challenges remain the same and there are many possible reasons such as manual handling, uneven plain surface causing blurry portions in the structure, etching effects, approximate values, lack of in number of experiments run.

Figure 22. Cementite network identification

High carbon steel is used for applications in which high strength, hardness, and wear resistance are necessary, such as wear parts, knives, saw blades, springs, gear wheels, chains, brackets etc. cold chisels, wrenches, Jaws for vices, pneumatic drill bits, wheels for railways service, wire for structural work, shear blades, hacksaws. (“High Carbon Steels” 2020)

Figure 23. Bar chart of BHN and tensile strength of specimens

The hardness test has shown us that Brinell hardness is the highest for water-quenched high carbon steel as expected because martensite is said to be the hardest and most brittle material. Similarly, the oil quenched steel is the 2nd most hard material. Since the ultimate tensile strength is related to the hardness of steel that's why if the hardness increases, tensile strength increases too. Hardness and tensile strength in the descending order:

Water quenched > Oil quenched > Normalized > Original > Cast iron > BSRM > Annealed > KSRM

Ductility:

Ductility refers to a material's ability to undergo plastic deformation, specifically elongation or stretching before it fractures. High-carbon steel has the highest toughness and hardness but the lowest ductility. Because high-carbon steels are always tempered and hardened, they are highly wear-resistant. (Kaveti 2023)

Ultimate Tensile Strength ↑ **Ductility** ↓ **(Relation 1)**

The ultimate tensile strength is inversely proportional to the ductility. If strength increases, then ductility decreases

Specimen	Ductility %
original	62.80%

An approximate chart of ductility from the experimental ultimate tensile strength chart is

annealing	90%
normalizing	49%
water quenching	21.80%
oil quenching	33.78%
Cast iron	77.60%
KSRM	100%
BSRM	81%

created. Since the tensile strength of KSRM is the lowest one, its ductility is the highest among these samples. That's why KSRM has been held as the reference to calculate an approximate percentage of ductility among these 8 specimens

Table: Comparison of ductility among the specimens

Heat Treatment Analysis

Three types of heat treatment were run on the high carbon steel. The heat treatment process changes the microstructure of the metal, making it more resistant to deformation and fracture. To reduce the internal stresses in metals. Metals can develop internal stresses during manufacturing or processing. These stresses can make the metal more susceptible to cracking or failure. From the carbon content analysis, it is seen that the amount of carbon content was reduced to 0.44 wt% for annealed steel and 0.52 wt% for normalized steel. The reason is very clear and it is caused by realigning grain structure using heat. The lower the carbon content, the higher the hardness. From *Figure 24*, the carbon content was found almost inversely proportional as tensile strength and hardness are higher for normalized steel than the annealed one.

C content ↑ **Tensile strength** ↑ **hardness** ↑ **(Relation 2)**

Figure 24. Chart of heat-treated specimens analysis

Figure 25. Bar chart of Ductility of specimens

Hardening: Water and oil quenching is a carbon diffuse less process and thus the carbon content can't be calculated. By the formation of martensite highest strength and hardness have been found in quenched steel. However, the cooling rate is another factor behind the martensitic structure. The faster the cooling rate, the higher the hardness and strength. (Relation 3) Water quenching is done through fast cooling whereas the cooling rate is lower in the case of oil quenching.

Cooling rate ↑ **Hardness** ↑ **Tensile strength** ↑ **(Relation 3)**

The higher the cooling rate of the quenching, the smaller the size of the grain size. Hence, it will increase the hardness of the steel. When the cooling rate is very high, it will increase the strength of the steel but it will reduce the toughness and the ductility of the steel. Higher cooling rate tends to make the steel become less flexible and more brittle (“Effect of heat-treatment on the hardness and mechanical properties of Boron Alloyed Steel” 1999)

A comparison table is shown below to distinguish the characteristics and properties of the heat-treated specimen

Annealing	Normalizing	Oil Quenching	Water Quenching
1. Refined grain structure than the elongated crystal size of the original one.	1. The initial cementite network is completely dissolved and thus we see finer grains than annealing.	1. Due to supersaturated solid solution of C atoms in a body-centered tetragonal (BCT) structure, Martensite is formed.	1. In this case the specimen was cooled faster than oil quenching and thus the microstructure seems non-homogeneous forming martensite.
2. Pearlite and Ferrite	2. Pearlite and Ferrite	2. Martensite	2. Martensite
3. Was cooled in the furnace	3. Was cooled in the air	3. Was cooled in oil	3. Was cooled in water
4. 0.44 wt %	4. 0.52 wt%	4. Carbon content can't be found.	4. Carbon content can't be found.
5. Most Ductile	5. More Ductile than annealed steel	5. More Ductile than water quenched steel	5. Least Ductile
6. A Process of softening material for improving machinability.	6. A final heat treatment for the material.	6. A process of hardening that is less brittle.	6. A process of hardening to strengthen the material the most.
7. Applications: In machining and improving electrical and magnetic properties.	7. Application: Automotive industry, Steel production	7. Application: Used in forgings and specially gearboxes parts	7. Application: typically used for low alloy steel grades that require a very rapid quench rate to achieve the desired hardness.

Cast Iron

Cast irons are a class of ferrous alloys with carbon contents above 2.14 wt%; in practice, however, most cast irons contain between 3.0 and 4.5 wt% C and, in addition, other alloying elements.

Figure 26. Fe - C phase diagram

A re-examination of the iron–iron carbide phase diagram (Figure 26) reveals that alloys within this composition range become completely liquid at temperatures above the eutectic line as it is easily melted and amenable to castings. In this case, the heating temperature is unknown. As there are several types of cast iron, it was uncertain which kind of cast iron we were dealing with but as the microstructure was characterized by the presence of flake graphite in Figure 26

The ferrous matrix. It was clear that the sample was of Grey Cast Iron. The experimental (Figure 27) and a reference microstructure of grey cast iron (Figure 27) are given below to compare similar structural characteristics:

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Figure 27. Graphite flask of cast iron

Experimentally 3.33 wt% of carbon content is found which matches the range of carbon content for cast iron. Now from relation 2 mentioned above shows that the hardness and strength should be increasing when carbon content should be increasing as well. Because of its high carbon content, it should have the most strength and hardness. However, its strength and hardness are medium compared to the other elements but not at its peak. This is because cast iron is an alloy, alloying is done with a motive to affect the mechanical properties, especially hardness, strength and that relation is only applicable for plain carbon steel.

Its good tensile strength, ductility, and effectiveness in damping vibrational energy represented in *Figure 28* grey cast iron is used in the applications of internal combustion engine cylinder blocks, flywheels, gearbox cases manifolds, etc.

Figure 28

KSRM VS BSRM

A huge part of this research is that we want to analyze the mechanical properties of KSRM and BSRM rods which is a plain mild carbon steel. Both are competing parallelly in the market. But in the metallurgical studies, we intended to compare their mechanical properties and which one is best suited for this country acknowledging the frequent earthquakes and geographical aspects. For that, a survey has been conducted to take valuable insights of the engineers who are working on the construction site, handling this kind of project, or who are experts in selecting suitable materials. To be more precise, this survey was only done to verify the experimental result with the practical life decisions.

Table for BHN and tensile strength of KSRM and BSRM

Specimen	BHN	Tensile Strength	Ductility	Carbon content
KSRM	206.52	712.14	100%	0.49 wt%
BSRM	254.6	877.92	81%	0.32 wt%

From Table 4.3 all of the data are calculated in a similar way that was used in the previous six experiments. Evidently, KSRM has a more carbon content of 0.49 wt% than BSRM with a carbon content of 0.32 wt%. both of these values satisfy the range of mild carbon steel which is 0.25 wt% to 0.60 wt%. According to relation 1 graph 4.6 is plotted and thus BSRM has more strength and if strength increases, hardness increases too (*Figure 28*), therefore BSRM is harder than KSRM although both of the specimens are of mild carbon steel.

Figure 29. Mechanical properties of KSRM and BSRM

Now another observation is that theoretically if Carbon content increases, Tensile strength and hardness should also increase since it is plain mild carbon steel. But in this case, the strength has increased with the decrease in carbon content. There might be some possible reason behind it. One of the big reasons is the specimen collected from the rod has already been through some heating process to be melted and again resolidified. Also, extrusion is a part of manufacturing rods which might have affected these mechanical properties. The relations that are formed here through the experiment are not the only factor and it is not linearly proportional.

Figure 30: Bar chart about the carbon content of KSRM and BSRM

So according to our experiment, BSRM takes over KSRM because BSRM has more tensile strength and hardness. But are these two mechanical properties enough for the selection process of rods? The survey says more about it that one of the major properties that should be considered in the first place is the *ultimate tensile strength* but there are definitely some other factors including durability, Corrosion Resistance, Weldability, Cost Availability, Environmental Impact, etc. But considering the current state of Bangladesh 8 responses were in favor of BSRM out of 11 responses which outstandingly matches our decision. According to these experts, BSRM has a lot of options for different criteria, and higher strength reduces the chances to collapse suddenly.

To conclude, BSRM is the best-suited rod because of its high tensile strength.

SURVEY REPORT:

This study examines the challenges of selecting the perfect alloy steel for structural engineering applications, focusing on the tensile strength, hardness, and microstructure of both KSRM and BSRM specimens. To justify our prediction with the practical field we made a survey with this type questions bellow:

In the selection of the best suited rod which mechanical property is considered at first?
11 responses

Figure 31.

According to the survey, 90.09% of experts favor ultimate tensile strength for structural engineering. A further 72.7 % of experts favor yield strength, ductility, and other mechanical properties in practical fields.

Is there any other factor that should be considered apart the mentioned properties?
11 responses

Figure 32 .

Figure 33 How many experts, after selecting the Ultimate Tensile Strength, prefer mechanical properties?

According to some experts -BSRM is commonly used due to its strength and durability, complies with BNBC provisions, and is used for maximum time in Bangladesh due to its high ductility and tensile strength, reducing the risk of collapse and providing more safety. Different corporate rods are utilized at different times based on economic decisions and usage situations. GPH Ispat, RSRM, etc. GPH Ispat is more cost-effective.

And some of the experts mentioned that KSRM is also greater. And some of them suggested that if weighing an alternative, the choice would be based on particular needs. An additional choice that offers a strong substitute for KSRM and BSRM is TATA Tiscon, which is renowned for its earthquake-resistant characteristics. The decision is based on several variables, such as engineering considerations and project-specific requirements.

The best earthquake-resistant construction materials have an important quality in common: high ductility. Ductility refers to the material's ability to move and change shape without breaking or losing strength. Traditionally, steel is the best and most common earthquake-resistant material. (“Background” 2020)

Figure 34

In terms of earthquake 72.7 % of experts went for BSRM steel because BSRM steel has more ultimate tensile strength. On the other hand BSRM steel with a minimum yield strength of

80,000 psi and tensile strength of 100,000 psi, along with a TY ratio of 1.25, offers better concrete placement and compaction (“BSRM Maxima” 2021)

Acknowledgment

Regardless, the similar nature of the error in this case also means that samples 1-3 and 4-5 percent composition data can be freely compared with each other without any significant irrelevancy. We can conclude that, from the software side, the biggest contributing factors to errors in this section are:

- Low resolution of the camera
- Human error in defining color range threshold parameters for the particle counting algorithm.

References

1. Askeland, Donald R. 2014. *Essentials of materials Science and Engineering*. 2nd ed. patparganj: Cengage learning.
2. “Background.” 2020. Earthquake Hazards Program. <https://earthquake.usgs.gov/education/shaking-simulations/background.php>.
3. “BSRM Maxima.” 2021. BSRM. <https://bsrm.com/maxima/>.
4. Cobb, Billy. 2021. “.” YouTube. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hardening_\(metallurgy\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hardening_(metallurgy)).
5. Cobb, Billy. 2021. “.” YouTube. <https://www.valvoline.com/en-eur/what-is-oil-quenching/>.
6. Cobb, Billy. 2021. “.” YouTube. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/28264688>.
7. “Compositon.” n.d. BSRM. Accessed December 29, 2023. <https://bsrm.com/vision-values/>.
8. “Effect of heat-treatment on the hardness and mechanical properties of Boron Alloyed Steel.” 1999. MATEC Web of Conferences. https://www.matec-conferences.org/articles/mateconf/pdf/2017/04/mateconf_aigev2017_01014.pdf.
9. “Heat Treatment Processes for Steel – IspatGuru.” 2020. IspatGuru. <https://www.ispatguru.com/heat-treatment-processes-for-steel/>.

10. "High Carbon Steels." 2020. Total Materia. <https://www.totalmateria.com/page.aspx?ID=CheckArticle&site=kts&NM=368>.
11. "ImageJ." 2015. Wikipedia. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ImageJ>.
12. K., Aliakbari. n.d. "Microstructure and fatigue fracture mechanism for a heavy-duty truck diesel engine crankshaft." *Scientia Iranica*. Accessed December 29, 2023. https://scientiairanica.sharif.edu/article_20780_b8d71041d47a1ee6508a97cf776e6929.pdf.
13. Kaveti, Bhavna. 2023. "Exploring the Impact of Carbon Content on Steel Strength and Ductility." *AZoM.com*. <https://www.azom.com/article.aspx?ArticleID=23259>.
14. McSwine, Damien. 2023. ".,." ., - YouTube. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780857090614500025>.
15. "Normalizing Process: Know Types, Advantages And Applications." 2023. Testbook. <https://testbook.com/mechanical-engineering/normalizing-process-definition-and-applications>.
16. "Quenching | Heat Treatment, Hardening & Tempering." 2023. Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/technology/quenching-materials-processing>.
17. "Sample Preparation." n.d. DoITPoMS. Accessed December 30, 2023. <https://www.doitpoms.ac.uk/tlplib/optical-microscopy/preparation.php>.
18. "Thermal Processing of Metals | nuclear-power.com." n.d. Nuclear Power. Accessed December 29, 2023. <https://www.nuclear-power.com/nuclear-engineering/metals-what-are-metals/heat-treatment-of-metals/thermal-processing-of-metals/>